

SYNTHETIC UTERUS MRI DATASET WITH UTERINE ORIENTATION LABELS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic medical images can augment training datasets where acquisition is costly or ethically constrained. In MRI imaging, subtle anatomical inconsistencies in synthetic images may reduce model generalisation if they deviate from plausible anatomy. We introduce SynthUterus ROI, a dataset of 800 region-of-interest (ROI)-cropped 96×96 synthetic uterus MRI images generated with diffusion models conditioned on uterine orientation. All images were independently annotated by clinicians for visual realism, orientation correctness and anomalies. SynthUterus ROI is designed for training and validation of (normative) medical imaging models, and is the first dataset to label uterus orientation explicitly. Publicly available at Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.18297879](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18297879)).

2. METHODS AND RESULTS

Images were generated using diffusion models trained on healthy, ROI-cropped uterine MRI scans [1]. To ensure privacy and diversity, generated images with SSIM > 0.4 to any training image or SSIM > 0.5 to previously generated images within the same class were rejected. Two third-year residents independently annotated all images following a calibration phase on 70 pre-labelled images (35 real, 35 synthetic) to harmonise criteria; these calibration images were excluded from analysis. Inter-annotator agreement was quantified using Cohen’s κ , with 95% confidence intervals estimated via 2,000-iteration non-parametric bootstrap. Agreement was substantial across most criteria and almost perfect for artefacts and anomalies, with $\kappa = 0.76$ for realism, 0.94 for orientation, 0.88 for artefacts, and 1.00 for anomalies. Both annotators rated most images as realistic and anatomically correct, with low rejection rates: non-realistic images 7.0 ± 2.2 %, incorrect classes 8.2 ± 0.4 %, artefacts 4.9 ± 0.8 %, and anomalies 0.2 %. Qualitative OOD analysis revealed recurring failure modes including texture striping (Fig. 1), cut-out organ contours, misaligned cavum lines, anatomical discontinuities, and globally implausible uterine structures, e.g., the cervix

Fig. 1. Representative out-of-distribution (OOD) synthetic images with failure modes: (a) texture striping and cut-out contours, (b) misaligned cavum line, (c) anatomical errors.

ending posteriorly and not in the vaginal canal, which primarily disrupt global anatomical coherence rather than local texture realism.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

SynthUterus ROI is a clinically annotated, generated synthetic uterus MRI dataset for training, validation, and OOD evaluation of deep learning models. High inter-annotator agreement and low rejection rates indicate most images are anatomically plausible, while observed OOD patterns highlight limitations of current generative models in capturing global anatomical coherence. By releasing SynthUterus ROI, we aim to enable reproducible research and standardised evaluation of uterine MRI data.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. This study was conducted in accordance with applicable ethical standards, and all clinical annotations followed relevant guidelines with ethical approval obtained where required.

4. REFERENCES

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